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A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF HRD CLIMATE ON PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES AND MANAGERES OF SHIPPING AND LOGISTICS COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

In this era of globalization the major task of an organization is its survival and sustainability in spite of cut-throat competition. Shipping and logistic being a service industry is dependent on the competencies of its employees. It is very important for the organization is to sharpen the competence of the employee and to motivate them to perform efficiently. HRD climate plays a crucial role in the development of the employees. The HRD climate ensures the proper implementation of OCTAPACE (Openness, Confrontation, Trust, Authenticity, Pro-action, Autonomy, Collaboration, Experimentation) culture and HRD systems in an organization which in-turn enhances the performance of the employees. The purpose of the study is to examine the impact of HRD climate on employee performance and to which extent it differs at the managers and executive level. The study reflects that the relationship of managers & employees are different on many factors taken into consideration for the analysis of HRD climate on performance of employees in shipping and logistic companies.

Key Words: OCTAPACE culture, employee performance, productivity, HRD climate, training, quality improvement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Resource Development (HRD) aims at creating values and culture conducive to individual growth in the organization. The performance of employees in an organization depends, to a large extent, on the existence of a favourable HRD climate. An organization enjoys competitive advantage when it is the only one which offers a product at a price and quality while its competitors cannot do so.

A human resource development is set of planned and systematic activities designed by an organization to provide opportunities to its members to learn skills necessary for the present and future job requirements. The process of HRD involves the development of expertise in the employee through organizational development and training and development. The aim of HRD is to improve the performance of the employees. The three main areas of human resource development are human resource management, quality improvement and career development. The term HRD climate as a concept evolved in India during eighties. Rao and Abraham (1986) were the first to study HRD climate. They defined the term 'HRD climate' as the shared perceptions which employees hold about that particular organization they work with. Human Resource Development (HRD) is a continuous process of developing employees' competency, dynamism, motivation and effectiveness in a systematic way. HRD involves the process through which the employees of the organization are prepared to give their best to achieve organization's objectives and bring optimal effectiveness in their jobs as well.

Rao, T. V. (1991) has stated that: —Human Resource Development (HRD), in organizational context, is a process by which the employees of an organizational are helped in a continuous and planned way to-

1. Acquire or sharpen capabilities required to perform various functions associated with their present or future expected roles.
2. Develop their general capabilities as individuals and discover and exploit their own inner potentials for their own and/or organizational development purposes.
3. Develop an organizational culture in which superior-subordinate relationship, teamwork, and collaboration among the sub-units are strong and contribute to the professional well-being, motivation and pride of the employees.

Organization now are facing greater their challenges to retain their competent employees with them. Besides talent management, improving the quality of HRD is reported to be one effective alternative to face these challenges. A productive and supportive environment is essential for effective learning and development of employees in organizations.

The present paper attempts to analyse and determine the relationship between HRD Climate, OCTAPACE Culture and performance of the employees i.e. the impact of HRD climate on employee performance in a logistic company. A

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